

DiSSCo Transition Project

**Further development of the functionality
of ELViS**

Work Package 3 - Deliverable 3.2

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Funded by the
European Union

Grant number 101130121

HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01-02 — Early phase implementation of ESFRI Projects
which entered the ESFRI Roadmap in 2018

HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions - Horizon Europe

27 May 2025

Version 1.3

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Project DiSSCo Transition**Grant Agreement n°** 101130121**Start of the project** 01 December 2023**Duration** 18 months**Project coordinator** Stichting Naturalis Biodiversity Center**Deliverable title** Further development of the functionality of ELViS**Deliverable n°** 3.2**Type of deliverable** Other**Work Package** 3**Lead Beneficiary** Muséum national d'histoire naturelle (MNHN)**Dissemination level** PU - Public

Griveau, M., DUSOULIER, F., Illien, G., Khalfoune, I., Le Pape, M., WORLEY, K., Weiland, C., & Addink, W. (2025). Further

Citation development of the functionality of ELViS - Deliverable 3.2 (v1.3). DiSSCo Transition Project.<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15357029>**Due date of deliverable** 31 May 2025**Actual submission date** 27 May 2025**Quality review** Yes**Deliverable status**

Version	Status	Date	Responsible	Actions
1.0	Draft 1.0	23 April 2025	Maxime Griveau, MNHN	Sent for review
1.0	Draft 1.0	28 April 2025	Claus Weiland, SGN Wouter Addink, Naturalis	Reviewed
1.0	Draft 1.1	30 April 2025	Maxime Griveau, MNHN	Incorporation of feedback from reviewers

1.1	Draft 1.1	30 April 2025	Gildas Illien, MNHN François Dusoulie, MNHN	Reviewed
1.1	Draft 1.2	02 May 2025	Maxime Griveau, MNHN	Incorporation of feedback from reviewers
1.2	Draft 1.2	06 May 2025	Maxime Griveau, MNHN	Sent for Coordinator verification
1.2	Draft 1.2	07 May 2025	Vânia Ferreira, Naturalis	Verified
1.2	Draft 1.2	07 May 2025	Maxime Griveau, MNHN	Sent for review
1.2	Draft 1.2	14 May 2025	Wouter Addink, Naturalis	Reviewed
1.2	Final 1.3	23 May 2025	Maxime Griveau, MNHN	Finalised, with incorporation of feedback from reviewers
1.3	Final 1.3	23 May 2025	Maxime Griveau, MNHN	Sent for Coordinator verification
1.3	Final 1.3	26 May 2025	Vânia Ferreira, Naturalis	Verified
1.3	Final 1.3	27 May 2025	Maxime Griveau, MNHN	Submitted

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Executive Summary

This document reports on the technical deliverable called [ELViS](#) (European Loans and Visits System), produced by the Muséum national d'histoire naturelle (Paris, France). The aim of this document is to set down on paper the elements considered at the key stage of the development of ELViS, which was the culmination of years of work by the DiSSCo community and the Muséum national d'histoire naturelle on the redesign of its local “Colhelper” tool (<http://colhelper.mnhn.fr> [soon closing]). This deliverable explains and details the process carried out during the development of ELViS, and also sets out the strategic elements and considerations that will enable the product to continue to mature in its definition.

Keywords

ELViS, Demonstrator, Product vision, FAIR, Digital Specimen Architecture, DSArch, DiSSCover, Specialisation plan

List of abbreviations

AAI – Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure

API – Application Programming Interface

CETAF – Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities

Colhelper – MNHN’s former request management application

DiSSCo – Distributed System of Scientific Collections

DiSSCover – DiSSCo’s platform for curating and annotating digital specimens

DTP – DiSSCo Transition Project

DSArch – Digital Specimen Architecture

ELViS – European Loans and Visits System

FAIR – Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable

FDO – FAIR Digital Objects

LtC – Latimer Core (standard)

MNHN – Muséum national d’histoire naturelle (Paris, France)

MUSE – My Museum request (MNHN’s new request management application)

RI – Research Infrastructure

RO – Research Output

SLA – Service Level Agreement

SSO – Single sign-on

SYNTHESYS+ – Synthesis of Systematic Resources Plus project

TRL - Technology Readiness Level

UI – User interface

UX – User experience

US – User story

WP – Work Package

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1. Introduction

This document formalises the work undertaken for the ELViS (European Loans and Visits System) deliverable, scheduled for completion by May 31, 2025. As defined in the project scope, the expected deliverable is:

"ELViS operating in a production environment managed by MNHN, with users migrated, integrated with the AAI core infrastructure, and connected to a new service supporting individual visits."

This document provides an overview of the project's background, primarily from MNHN's perspective (MUSE project), as ELViS' history is already well documented in the SYNTHESYS+¹ deliverables referenced further below. The core focus will be on the demonstrator deliverable, detailing the key steps leading to its development, including the rationale behind choosing a demonstrator, the methodology adopted, and the functionalities embedded.

Additionally, we will explain the development decisions made, their alignment with ELViS' long-term strategy and where these led to differences between the planned and delivered product.

Finally, this document will present the steps towards a long-term shared product vision, providing essential information on priorities, timelines, and future development pathways. The report will conclude with a proposed roadmap for ELViS' next phases.

2. Aims of the product

The aim is the implementation of a pan-European system for transnational and virtual access to natural science collections as one of the core DiSSCo services. Today, researchers must navigate through a multitude of databases, deal with administrative complexities and overcome budgetary constraints to access specimens. ELViS aims to transform this reality by offering a single point of access for:

- Visit collections
- Borrow specimens
- Access digitisation services (2D and 3D)
- Ask for sampling

The primary aim of the product is to reduce barriers and improve research efficiency for researchers interested in natural science specimens. This is done by making it easy to find out what material is available, where, what the access conditions are, and requesting access without having to go to each individual institution. ELViS will help scientists decide if a collection visit is necessary and guide them to the closest location of suitable specimens. ELViS also aims to improve collection usage monitoring and trackability by providing a simple tool that will allow collection managers to closely follow their specimens as they are borrowed. The last aim of the product is to improve citation

¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/823827>

tracking: each time a specimen is requested, any subsequent publications will be traced in the application.

3. Main audience

At a progress meeting between MNHN and the DiSSCo team, it was pointed out that the project needed two channels of information: technical and strategic². This document is aimed at both. On the other hand, as its main objective is to be a milestone guiding the decision-making process for the future development of ELViS, the strategic elements will be highlighted, and the more technical elements appended. They are also essential to the decision-making process, but are here to ensure that information on the technical aspects of ELViS circulates as effectively as possible among the technical team. So the main audiences for this document are both the technical staff doing further service development and the future DiSSCo ERIC.

4. Project history

4.1. MNHN's side: MUSE project

The My Museum request (MUSE) project was launched a few years ago, and is part of a more global strategy of modernisation of the information system of the general management delegated to collections. The first objective was to replace the Colhelper tool, which was ageing, with a new application named MUSE. Seeing the opportunity to mutualise the developments, MNHN proposed to DiSSCo's community to take the responsibility of the development of ELViS, which will be the equivalent of MUSE at the European scale (thus, adding multi-institutionalisation functionalities). In this way, the MUSE project was, since its conception, developed to become ELViS one day.

This is reflected in the project's architectural choices, which are the same as DiSSCo's core infrastructure: Keycloak for authentication, JavaScript frameworks (React) for the front office, Kubernetes for deployment, etc³.

Another point to note is that, because of the exceptionally generous size of MNHN's collections, their complexity and the differences in their organisation, a great deal of conceptualisation work had to be carried out to match a common tool to remarkably diverse practices. For example, the three roles of MUSE: dispatcher, decision-maker and preparer, and their combination, make MUSE a highly adaptable tool outside MNHN. Another example: as each collection set has specific access rules corresponding to each of the needs available in the application, the application already incorporates a means of varying access conditions very finely. This means that some MUSE functions are already partially multi-institutional.

² WP3 - Task 3.2 Meeting of 26/06/2024 to update DiSSCo partners on the development of MUSE/ELViS

³ See the "ELViS' technical architecture" section for more details.

4.1.1. Gathering user requirements

Before discussing the gap analysis carried out between the functionalities required in MUSE and those required in ELViS, we need to take a moment to review the methodology used to gather requirements for the two applications. It was essential to bear this in mind when studying the differences, to be able to compare requirements with an awareness of the possible pitfalls and differences between the methods used to collect them.

First, let us mention the collection of user needs at MNHN, which was carried out in the form of workshops organised with the various Colhelper users, leading to the writing of 185 user stories. The user stories for ELViS were collected in the “Workflow integration workshop” of SYNTHESYS+ and included in the milestone MS52 of the project (Blettery et al. 2023)⁴. Some of them were also directly collected on DiSSCo’s GitHub repository for ELViS⁵.

Regarding the gap analysis, the reader can refer to deliverable D6.6 of SYNTHESYS+ titled Results of pilot workflow integrations with ELViS (Blettery et al. 2023)⁶. This study served as the starting point for building the ELViS backlog (for both the demonstrator and version 1).

4.2. DiSSCo’s side: ELViS project

We will be very brief on the history of the ELViS project, considering that it is already well documented in the various deliverables of the SYNTHESYS+ project, so we will limit ourselves to indicating the references of the deliverables related to the project. The main goal here is that, as we will re-implement some of the previous ELViS code using a different technology stack to overcome some technical debt and align with current technical needs, these deliverables will allow us to reuse some of the work that has been carried out during the creation of this application, and significantly if we want to re-add the Calls functionalities (i.e., the structured and time-bound submission windows during which researchers could apply for physical or virtual access to collections and services offered by institutions participating in the SYNTHESYS+ network).

Sharif Islam, Helen Hardy, Scott Wilson | “ELViS is in the building: The European Loans and Visits System and first experiences with Transnational and Virtual Access”

- https://www.academia.edu/88435572/ELViS_is_in_the_Building_The_European_Loans_and_Visits_System_and_first_experiences_with_Transnational_and_Virtual_Access

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<https://www.synthesys.info/content/dam/nhm-synthesys/synthesys-plus-deliverables/SYNTHESYS%2B%20D6.6.pdf>, page 7.

⁵ <https://github.com/DiSSCo/user-stories>

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<https://www.synthesys.info/content/dam/nhm-synthesys/synthesys-plus-deliverables/SYNTHESYS%2B%20D6.6.pdf>, page 7-18.

- *Abstract: Summary of the release of Picturae's ELViS (2021)*

Wim Van Dongen, Wouter Addink, Sharif Islam | Deliverable 6.4 (SYNTHESYS+) “ELViS: a System for Unified Access”

- [https://www.synthesys.info/content/dam/nhm-synthesys/synthesys-plus-deliverables/SYNTHESYS%2B%20D6.4 ELViS System for Unified Access.pdf](https://www.synthesys.info/content/dam/nhm-synthesys/synthesys-plus-deliverables/SYNTHESYS%2B%20D6.4%20ELViS%20System%20for%20Unified%20Access.pdf)
- *Abstract: Technical summary of the release of Picturae's ELViS (2021)*

Margret Steinhorsdottir, Wouter Addink, Sharif Islam, Sabine Von Mering, Julia Pim Reis, Kevin Holston | Deliverable 6.5 (SYNTHESYS+) “Specification and requirements for integrations with ELViS”

- <https://www.synthesys.info/content/dam/nhm-synthesys/synthesys-plus-deliverables/SYNTHESYS%2B%20Deliverable%20D6.5.pdf>
- *Abstract: Specifications for ELViS' future development after the release Picturae's ELViS (2021)*

Jonathan Blettery, Sarah Gauthier de Saint-Mathieu, Katharine Worley, François Dusoulier, Francis Clément, Gildas Illien, Wouter Addink | Deliverable 6.6 (SYNTHESYS+) “Results of pilot workflow integrations with ELViS”

- <https://www.synthesys.info/content/dam/nhm-synthesys/synthesys-plus-deliverables/SYNTHESYS%2B%20D6.6.pdf>
- *Abstract: Gap analysis between ELViS specification and MUSE ones. (2023)*

Code of Picturae's ELViS:

- <https://github.com/DiSSCo/elvis-frontend>
- <https://github.com/DiSSCo/elvis-backend>

4.3. Re-implementation post SYNTHESYS+

4.3.1. Rationale

A few years have passed since the first version of ELViS was developed in SYNTHESYS+, in which the code was maintained but not further developed, while a wealth of new development was done in the DiSSCo Core infrastructure and, also, there were new technological developments such as MUSE. This made significant changes in technology necessary, and some of the functionality needs to be re-implemented to overcome this technical debt and adjust to current user needs and priorities.

4.3.2. Archiving

As part of the transition to an environment managed by the MNHN while maintaining the <https://elvis.dissco.eu> URL, a preventive archiving of the data from the previous ELViS

version, developed by Picturae in the SYNTHESYS+ project, has been carried out. This process took place in two stages:

1. Extraction and structuring of institutional data: Information related to institutions was retrieved and stored in an SQLite database, following a simplified data model to facilitate potential future reuse.
2. Archiving of request data: All requests made during the two years of application use have been recorded in a CSV file. Additionally, the automatically generated PDFs containing more detailed information about each request have been downloaded.

Each file is named using the requester's name, the request date, and an identifier corresponding to the request number, sorted in reverse chronological order.

Thus, requesters wishing to access information about their past requests can submit a request to the ELViS application Product Owner, who will provide temporary access. Additionally, a request has been submitted to the European Commission's archives service to determine the administrative retention period and assess the possibility of permanent archiving for certain request-related information.

5. May 2025 deliverable

The delivered application, in production, can be found at <https://elvis.dissco.eu>.

The code, documented in English for both front and back office, has an Apache 2.0 open source licence and can be found on DiSSCo's GitHub: <https://github.com/DiSSCo> under the name "elvis-mnhn-frontend", "elvis-mnhn-backend" and "elvis-mnhn-data". It will sync automatically with the local Gitlab to make sure that the code stays up to date with what's online.

5.1. Technology readiness level

Before going into details on the delivered functionalities, we need to precise the technology readiness level⁷ (TRL) of the deliverable. The deliverable is a product running in an operational environment managed by MNHN, which means that ELViS was advanced to TRL level 7: prototype developed and demonstrated in an operational environment. This means it is not yet a production version of the service but rather a demonstrator, although it does demonstrate working functionality for e.g. requesting a visit or loan and is available in an operational environment. This readiness level answers various strategic and technical aims that we will detail below.

⁷<https://www.emdesk.com/horizon-2020-horizon-europe-basics-guide/what-is-the-technology-readiness-level-and-why-is-it-important-for-eu-funding>

5.1.1. Validate requirements and refine specifications

A gap analysis⁸ revealed that ~90% of the functionalities required in ELViS are covered with the delivered product, with the notable exception of multi-institutional management. Rather than immediately committing to complex and costly developments in this area, the demonstrator will enable us to test the tool with the community, assess its acceptability and adjust certain functionalities if necessary. This approach limits the risk of developing irrelevant elements and ensures a better match with institutional expectations. What is more, a demonstrator gives future users a concrete view of the complete project, except for the integration of several institutions that are not in the line of sight for processing requests. They therefore could see a finalised, ready-to-use tool and give their feedback on the heart of ELViS: the filing, tracking and processing of requests. This removes certain reservations and strengthens the commitment of institutions.

5.1.2. Ensuring alignment with MUSE developments

MUSE developments, which are still in progress, include several features that are indispensable for ELViS. It would be premature to create a fork of MUSE for ELViS, as this would involve a complex merge to reintegrate these developments later (for example, the addition of a chat between requesters and collection managers, or the ability to attach documents to a request). The demonstrator thus enables ELViS to be evaluated without the risk of premature technical divergence or unnecessary investments.

5.1.3. Consider dependencies on the Specialisation Plan

It should also be noted that ELViS relies heavily on the Specialisation Plan (WP2, Task 2.2), but also on DiSSCo's Digital Specimen Architecture (DSArch) (WP3, Task 3.1). As these products have not reached a sufficient level of maturity or content, it is impossible to effectively develop the multi-institutional mode of ELViS. The demonstrator, therefore, enables progress to be made on other aspects of the project without compromising the overall coherence of the development. From a very concrete point of view, it also enables a list of requirements to be created for ELViS, and notably the application's Latimer Core (LtC) profile⁹ (Woodburn et al. 2022), which lists all the data it will need to operate in “multi-institutional mode”, to ensure that the Specialisation Plan service will be able to match them all.

5.1.4. Facilitate strategic decisions for the next stage of the project

Finally, the feedback obtained from the demonstrator will enable us to draw up a more robust roadmap for future development and establish a long-term product vision (this is the aim of the go product roadmap workshop to be discussed below). This will make it possible to identify the critical functionalities to be prioritised and those that can be adjusted or left aside, and to define a clearer framework and priorities for the rest of the project and the associated decision-making.

⁸<https://www.synthesys.info/content/dam/nhm-synthesys/synthesys-plus-deliverables/SYNTHESYS%2B%20D6.6.pdf>, page 10

⁹ https://github.com/Maxime-Griveau/ELViS/tree/main/LtC_profile_ELViS

5.2. MUSE integration methodology

Before detailing the functionalities that the ELViS application will include, it is essential to briefly explain the development methodology. This will help to clarify the constraints that influence the project's technical choices.

To ensure ELViS remains aligned with MUSE while leveraging its functionalities, we have adopted a "feature flipping" approach. This methodology allows us to integrate MUSE's developments without forking the project prematurely. The primary reason for this decision is that MUSE is still evolving, and forking at this stage would introduce significant challenges, particularly when it comes to merging future updates.

By using feature flipping, we can selectively enable "ELViS features" within an instance of MUSE. However, this also implies that we are temporarily constrained in terms of structural changes. ELViS must remain closely aligned with MUSE's architecture, which means we cannot implement deep modifications or significant deviations. While this solution is currently the most effective given the state of MUSE's development, a true fork will become necessary once MUSE reaches a stable and mature state. At that point, ELViS will require a more autonomous development path to fully accommodate its specific multi-institutional functionalities.

Also, to further streamline the integration and ensure a coherent development process, we have retained the same development team across both projects. This approach not only preserves technical consistency but also optimised resource allocation, allowing us to accelerate ELViS' development while minimising potential integration issues.

5.3. Embedded functionalities

5.3.1. MUSE functionalities

Before diving into the specific functionalities that have been feature-flipped in the ELViS instance, we must first explore the core functionalities of MUSE, as they form the foundation of what ELViS is. As previously mentioned, the aim of MUSE is to replace the old Colhelper tool, which was used to submit requests related to collections. MUSE therefore incorporates its key functionalities: submitting a request (loan, visit, sampling, garden observation, digitisation) and its processing by the collection manager, up until the reception of specimens and publications.

The main innovations introduced by MUSE are:

- For each type of user profile (e.g., scientist, artist, exhibition manager) and each type of project (e.g., scientific research, exhibition, educational initiative), workflows are fully customised, as they are for several types of needs (loans, visits, etc.).
- A major change brought by MUSE is that requesters can submit requests concerning multiple collection sets with multiple needs, all grouped under the concept of a "project."¹⁰

¹⁰ For instance, if one wants to do a taxonomic revision about Corsican marine specimens, one will submit a single project and may ask for samples of vertebrates, as well as loans of invertebrates.

- In addition to these improvements, MUSE introduces numerous features which will bring comfort and ergonomony to collection managers, including:
 - A dashboard and notifications to track request progress.
 - Pre-filled documents (such as the loan agreement).
 - The ability to update and roll back any step in the request submission and processing workflow.
 - A built-in chat function for direct communication between the requester and the collection manager.
 - Statistics and reporting functionalities.¹¹

As we implement feature flipping, specific functionalities under development in MUSE are progressively being integrated into the ELViS instance (e. g. the administration dashboard, Figure 5). These include graphical alignment with DiSSCo's graphic scheme (Figure 1 and 3), translation features, email notifications, and connection to the core digital specimen infrastructure API to retrieve specimen data (Figure 2). As a result, the resources allocated to MUSE directly benefit ELViS, ensuring alignment between the two systems. This is further reinforced by the merger of both backlogs, allowing for a more efficient development process and seamless integration of MUSE's advancements into ELViS. In very concrete terms, this alignment of backlogs has enabled us to prioritise the institutional dashboard in MUSE, as it is especially important for ELViS. (Figure 4).

EUROPEAN COLLECTIONS

Figure 1. ELViS' current homepage

Figure 2. Example of a DOI retrieved from DiSSCo's central hub

¹¹ Planned in December 2025.

Figure 3. Notification received by the requester

Figure 4. Institution administration dashboard

Figure 5. Roles administration dashboard

5.3.2. Deviations from planned functionality

While reading the list of functionalities embedded in ELViS, we can note some differences with the planned functionality: “ELViS running in an operational environment managed by MNHN, its users migrated and connected to the AAI core infrastructure component and connected with a new service for supporting individual visits”.

Let us first look at the functionalities aligned with the deliverable:

- ELViS is running in a fully operational environment – <https://elvis.dissco.eu> – managed by MNHN IT services.
- The new service supporting individual visits is implemented.

Also, the deliverable connects with the DiSSCo core data infrastructure through its API to get specimen information, which enables users to find specimens by their digital specimen DOI.

Then, let us list the functionalities that are not implemented as originally planned:

- ELViS’ users are not migrated from Picturae’s prototype version, the reason for that is that we were not authorised to do that as stated in GDPR, article 5:

“1. Personal data must be:

a) processed lawfully, fairly and transparently with respect to the data subject (lawfulness, fairness, transparency).

[...]

c) adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary for the purposes for which they are processed (data minimization).”¹²

As users were not informed of a future migration when they registered in Picturae’s application and the privacy policy did not take this into account, we were not authorised to migrate user accounts or other personal data to the new version. As a solution, the data from the previous ELViS system was archived. Users will need to register again in the new ELViS, but can then request access to the archived data from the requests they made in the old version, in case they would need it in the future. It is highly unlikely that they need this, though, as these requests have already been handled a few years ago.

- As for the connection to the Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI), this could not be achieved because it was a structural change in the application, which was not possible because of the development decision to follow a feature flipping approach. Also, the DiSSCo AAI provision was under change during ELViS development, moving from GRNET¹³ to another provider. However, for

¹² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/FR/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX%3A32016R0679>, Article 5 (page 35).

¹³ Greek Research and Technology Network

authentication and authorisation the same technical solution (Keycloak) was implemented and since there are no users to migrate, switching to the DiSSCo AAI service in the future would require very little work.

5.3.3. Technical choices made

The technical architecture of MUSE is closely aligned with that of the DiSSCo core data infrastructure, ensuring consistency and interoperability between the two systems (Figure 6). Both initiatives adopt technology stacks centred on Java and JavaScript ecosystems, combining backend services primarily developed in Java with frontend components built using frameworks such as React and Node.js. This shared foundation supports a modular, service-oriented architecture and lays the groundwork for a coherent integration strategy between the platforms.

Both projects also follow a continuous integration and deployment (CI/CD) workflow and rely on Kubernetes for container orchestration. This strategic choice enables efficient deployment, scalability, and management of microservices, contributing to a flexible and resilient infrastructure that can adapt to evolving needs.

In terms of data management, both systems utilise PostgreSQL as their primary relational database management system. This common technological base facilitates compatibility and data integration, while ensuring robust performance for the handling of structured information.

To promote interoperability and streamline development, both MUSE and DiSSCo expose their APIs through Swagger. This ensures the production of standardised, machine-readable API documentation, making it easier for third-party services and developers to integrate and interact with the platforms.

Finally, for authentication and access control, both infrastructures integrate Keycloak. This provides a unified approach to identity and access management, allowing for secure, centralized user authentication and authorisation across components, and enhancing the overall user experience.

Through these shared architectural principles and technologies, MUSE and the DiSSCo core data infrastructure establish a strong technical alignment, fostering seamless interoperability and supporting the emergence of a cohesive, scalable digital ecosystem.

Figure 6. ELViS' technical architecture

6. Development of a long-term product vision

6.1. Methodology

To develop a long-term and shared product vision for further development of the service, two workshops were conducted: one with DiSSCo's technical coordinator and another internally with the MNHN team. Each workshop followed the same structured approach to align expectations, define objectives, and explore implementation scenarios.

Key discussions included:

- Defining the long-term vision and core objectives of the service. **“Where we aim to be”**.
- Presenting and evaluating different implementation scenarios, highlighting their advantages and challenges. **“What's the priority?”**.
- Using the picked scenario, follow a “go product roadmap” canvas to distinguish the project phases, and for each one of them, the aims, the dates, the target users and success metrics and goals. **“What path should we follow to achieve our aim considering the priority?”**
- The last phase of the workshop was focused on key questions that we judged important to get answers to (in order mostly to avoid implicit – that is, to make

assumptions explicit and ensure that all stakeholders share a common understanding rather than relying on unspoken expectations).

6.2. Results

Both workshops had a different focus. The first one, with the DiSSCo technical coordinator, was more focused on the technical priorities and the development roadmap (see appendix 2); while the second workshop, which mobilised a more functional and political team, was more focused on the product vision, risk analysis and the political/strategic roadmap. At the end, the two workshops complemented each other nicely, enabling us to establish a clear list of questions that will need to be addressed with the DiSSCo community for further development: whether on the technical, strategic or functional scope (some are affecting the three). These are listed in the following table (note that now the questions are more on the strategic side, but they will raise both functional and technical questions when answered).

Table 1. Questions on next steps for ELViS to be addressed by the DiSSCo community

Strategic	Functional	Technical
<p>What would be the boundary between what is managed in “centralised” ELViS and what remains locally managed? (as well as the data)</p> <p>How do we manage responsibilities and roles for ELViS regarding DiSSCo’s current organisation? What is the best scope for the service? (Each institution, group of institutions, national nodes...)</p> <p>What are the requirements to get onboarded in ELViS?</p> <p>How do we manage “bottle in the sea” requests (i.e. requests which are not addressed to a specific institution) on the political side (they may require a dedicated team/desk to handle and dispatch these)?</p> <p>How shall we manage potential future calls (will</p>	<p>Will the added value be enough to make institutions change their current access workflows into an ELViS-centric one?</p> <p>How do we manage “bottle in the sea” requests (huge business value for serving researchers)?</p> <p>Is FDO (FAIR Digital Objects) implementation a priority?</p> <p>What support, training and documentation resources should be provided to accompany onboarding and ensure smooth adoption by local teams?</p> <p>What indicators and reporting functionalities (dashboards, usage statistics, performance monitoring) are required for both end users and central administrators?</p>	<p>How do we manage “bottle in the sea” requests (i.e. requests which are not addressed to a specific institution) (technical filters and way to direct requests to the correct institution)? Are they directed to multiple institutions? If so, with what limits?</p> <p>How do you define, test and maintain filtering criteria and thresholds for “bottle in the sea” requests (geographical distance, specialisation plan, human capacity) in order to automate referrals as effectively as possible?</p> <p>What do we do with the calls (is it possible to implement them in the current architecture)?</p> <p>What are the technical requirements to get onboarded in ELViS?</p>

<p>there be another 'SYNTHESYS-like' project in the future)?</p> <p>What funding and sustainability models (service fees, recurring calls for projects, national contributions) will be defined to ensure ELViS remains operational and evolves?</p>		<p>Is it possible to automate the onboarding process?</p> <p>What are ELViS' technical dependencies?</p>
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6.3. Proposed roadmap for further development

Between 2025 and 2026, a series of workshops will be organised to address both the **functional** and **strategic** dimensions of the ELViS project. From a functional perspective, the focus will be on continued gathering and analysing of user needs in order to take into account both the business vision and the technical vision of the product. This process will support the development of functional and adaptation scenarios, which are essential to assess the long-term technical and financial feasibility. In parallel, from a political standpoint, the workshops will also serve to propose organisational scenarios that take into account the various institutional and governance considerations, thereby laying the groundwork for the decision-making phases to follow.

During the period from 2026 to 2027, MNHN proposes a two-tiered "Go/No-Go" decision process. The first decision will be made on MNHN's side, based on the outcomes of the feasibility assessments and the functional scenarios established during the previous phase. If this internal review is positive, the second decision will take place at the DiSSCo governance level, where the organisational scenarios will be evaluated to determine the broader institutional acceptability of the project. This phase will lead to a strategic decision regarding both the operational and strategic trajectory of ELViS. The formal commitment to raise up the level of development as discussed with the users is anticipated for early 2027. MNHN proposes to not continue technical development until then, except for – maybe – some adjustments / tests using the demonstrator.

Figure 7. ELViS' proposed roadmap

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8. Appendices

Appendix 1: Development priorities “go product roadmap”

Version Name	V1 – MVP – Multi-institutional ELViS	V2 – "Make it ELViS!"	V3 – Extend to other users beyond researchers, automate onboarding
Target Users	Researchers only	Researchers only	Researchers and others (MUSE's current audience)
Goals	Fork MUSE to create an MVP and integrate multi-institutional support for 3 target institutions.	Onboard 10–20 institutions per year from this version onward. Calls functionality? Turning ELViS' requests into FAIR digital objects (FDO)? “Bottle in the sea” requests?	Automated onboarding process: the goal is for at least half of DiSSCo countries to have at least one institution in ELViS (total: 50).
Success Metrics	20% of onboarded institutions' requests go through ELViS. 2000 requests per year from this version onward.	50 institutions in ELViS, 5000 requests per year.	

Appendix 2: Macro Product backlog for ELViS

- UX/UI design
- FAIR digital object
- Connection to CETAF API (specialisation plan)
- Connexion to DiSSCo's API (core infrastructure)
- Translations
- Connection to the core AAI (SSO)
- Information pages
- Request handling
- Feedback
- Roles management
- Documents management
- Institution's dashboard
- Calls
- Change management (Onboarding process)